

**A DEEP LEARNING FRAMEWORK FOR FACE RECOGNITION:
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF YUNET AND MULTI TASK CNN DETECTORS****T.A.S.L. PRASANNA**MSC CS, Department of Information Technology & Computer Application
Andhra University College of Engineering, Andhra University.aswinateku967@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

A Python-based video face recognition system that can identify, detect, and save faces from video input is designed and improved in this work. Detection models, such as YuNet, CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) and MTCNN (Multi-Tasked Cascaded Convolutional Networks), are included into the system to balance performance and accuracy. It features reporting with facial image capture, model path correction, and strong error management. The change in models based on performance for real-time applications are highlighted by a comparative study of the two models. The improved system can be used for surveillance and attendance applications because it is reliable and portable.

Keywords

YuNet, MTCNN, Face Detection, Image Capture, and Face Recognition.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, face recognition technology has become increasingly remarkable in areas such as security monitoring, classroom appearance and automatic access control. As the demand for real-time identity verification and video-based monitoring increases, the need for accurate and practical facial recognition systems has also increased. Thanks to open-source libraries like OpenCV, DLIB, and face_recognition, developers now have access to powerful tools that make it easy to build and deploy face recognition systems on everyday computers without the need for expensive hardware [13]. The project presents a real-time face recognition and reporting system designed for practical use in educational institutions, small organizations and monitoring applications. The system uses a flexible design to separate functions such as face detection, face recognition, image saving and report generation. It supports a wide variety of face detection models, each have different speed and accuracy characteristics [14, 18]. This allows flexibility users to choose the best model based on hardware (CPU/GPU) and their specific application needs. The part of the face recognition is based on facenet idea, where each face is converted into a 128-dimensional vector (embedding) for fast and reliable matching. What makes this system makes it support for custom dataset. Instead of relying on large public dataset, we made our own by recording the face of friends and classmates using a webcam or camera. These images are again encoded and used to identify people in real time. Whenever a known face is detected, the system records the name and time of appearance. If the face is not recognized, the system saves the cropped image of the unknown person in a folder to review for future. These characteristics are particularly useful for attendance monitoring, safe access and even forensic reviews. The system also generates a report that stores all the photos of persons who are present in the video. The model can be used offline, which means that it does not require internet access to work. By combining real-time video input, the flexible model support and detailed reporting helps the proposed structure to pull the gap between academic facial recognition research and real world day-to-day applications. It is a complete and adaptable solution suitable for schools, colleges and small businesses.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section looks at some of the important work done in face detection and recognition, especially the systems that work on videos in real time. One of the key ideas in modern face recognition comes from FaceNet, introduced by Schroff et al. [1] which takes a person's face and turns it into a kind of patterns using a 128-dimensional code, that

makes it easy to compare faces using simple math. While it was mostly used on still images but many real-time systems today are built on this concept. Singh et al. [2] used older but faster techniques like HOG features combined with SVM classifiers. These work well on computers without powerful graphics cards. Jain et al. [3] also showed that these traditional methods can still be useful in situations where we need speed more than complex accuracy like when running on regular laptops or small devices. Sharma et al. [4] combined OpenCV and Dlib to build a real-time face detection system. They used classic methods like Haar Cascade for detecting faces and HOG for recognizing them. Patel et al. [5], compared older algorithms with newer deep learning models. They found that while deep learning (like CNNs) is more accurate, traditional models are still good enough for small devices or CPU-based systems. Xu et al. [6] built a system for edge devices like routers, that helps fast detection with deeper verification checks. Their design influenced how we structured our model-switching setup, where the user can choose between fast or accurate detection. Singh et al. [7] did a survey of face detection methods in videos and highlighted how different models perform in different lighting or change in movement. Guo et al. [8] came up with a clever idea to make recognition more reliable even when the surroundings or lighting are very different. Mansour et al. [9] compared commercial face recognition tools with open-source libraries like face_recognition and found pros and cons for both. Kumar et al. [10] used Mobile Net and Arc Face to create a lightweight face recognition model that can run on low-powered devices like Raspberry Pi. That encouraged us to test CNN-based models in our system too. Hu et al. [11] reviewed several CNN architectures to find which ones work best in real-time. Yi et al. [12] talked about training deep models from scratch using huge datasets, and King [13] developed Dlib, a toolkit we used for detecting and encoding faces. Roy et al. [14] created a face recognition system for surveillance that runs in real time using free software. Sharma et al. [15] compared multiple algorithms to see how well they perform under different conditions, like poor lighting or when someone's face is partially hidden. Wang et al. [19] made a face recognition system for classroom using Python. Singh et al. [18] explored how combining HOG and CNN can improve performance in live video. These works showed that using more than one model can be helpful.

III. METHODOLOGY

Video-based facial identification and reporting system was designed using a step-by-step modular design, which means each part of the system has its own clear work, and everything works together in a smooth flow. The first step in face recognition systems starts by loading the known faces that we had saved. These are the faces of people that we want to identify, and each is stored as a type of digital fingerprint (called encoding) that makes it easier to compare the faces later. At the same time, the system takes video input. This can be from a live webcam or a video file that we have already recorded. The video is broken into separate frames, so we can see each frame at a time. This helps the system to function in real time, processing each frame when it comes. Next, the system looks for a face in each frame. It supports a group of various models such as YuNet, and MTCNN, which uses different ways to spot faces. Depending on how powerful the computer is, you can choose the model to use. Once a face is found, the system puts a box around it and only focuses on that part of the frame. Then face encoding step comes. Here, the system takes each detected face and turns it into a unique set of numbers. These numbers help the system to find out the individual by comparing them with the people stored in the list of known faces. If the system recognizes someone's face, it shows their name on the screen and notes the exact time seen in the video. If it does not recognize the person, it marks them as "unknown", takes a picture of their face, and saves it into the folder. In this way, we can check who they are later and even add them to our list when needed. The system finds everything such as who appeared, when they appeared, and any unknown people are saved in a clean report. These reports are useful for things like attendance or safety.

Fig:1 Methodology

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

This represents the results obtained from evaluating two face detection models that are used in this project. Its purpose was to identify known individuals, unknown faces and access their time of appearance in summary output from video input as shown in Fig. 2 and saves the report in folder as shown in Fig. 3. Comparison focuses on several dimensions, including accuracy, performing on unknown faces, processing speed and overall suitability for CPU-based systems. Model comparison summary done on two face detection models are used for face recognition and reporting, focuses individually to ensure a fair and standardized evaluation between YuNet and MTCNN. Their performance was measured using similar video input and system configurations. Table 1 summarizes the consequences of this comparative study. We tested our facial identification and reporting system using two different face detection models YuNet and MTCNN to see how well they have worked in real-life situations. Both models were tested in the same setup so that we could significantly compare how they perform by spotting both known and unknown faces in a video. We saw how accurate they were, how fast they worked on a regular computer (without GPU), and how reliable they were.

Table 1 Performance Evaluation

Model	Detection Accuracy	Handling of Unknown Faces	Execution Speed (CPU)	Overall Performance Summary
YuNet	Consistently accurate for medium-range faces	Detected and reported well (if lingered)	Fast and lightweight	Most practical and stable for CPU-based systems
MTCNN	Expected to be high but not achieved here	Struggled due to long processing time	Very slow without GPU	Requires GPU to be effective; impractical on CPU setups

Among the two, YuNet gave the most balanced performance. It was able to detect facial detection in the general lighting and from the front, all were running quickly and smoothly without high-end systems. On the other hand, MTCNN, although it is known to be accurate, slowed down on our setup and not in real time. From this we found out how important it is to choose a model that fits the hardware you are using, especially if you are working on a basic machine. We conducted many real-world tests to see how our system behaves in various video situations. In a test, we used a video, in which there was no person. As expected, the system did not detect any facial and did not increase any false alarm, which shows that it works well even when there is nothing in the video.

Fig.2 Summary Report of Video

Fig. 3 Output Folder

In another test, we used a video with a lot of unknown people. The system was able to detect their facial, but it only recorded those who remained in the frame for a long time. This is because the system is designed only to log the faces that are clearly visible for more than a few seconds, it helps to capture the blurred or quick appearance. When the faces were away from the camera or appeared too small, both models struggled a bit. But compared to others, these handled the difficult cases a bit better, which makes it more reliable when working with regular, low-end systems.

V. CONCLUSION

In this project, we produced and tested a real-time facial recognition and report generating system that is both flexible and easy to manage. We tried different face detection models such as every YuNet and MTCNN to see how well they work in real-world video situations. We found that MTCNN model may be very accurate, but they often slow down on the system without a powerful GPU. On the other hand, models like YuNet gave us a good balance, they were sharp, accurate enough, and easy to run on basic computers. Our system is designed in a modular manner, meaning that each part such as facial detection, identifying them and reporting results works independently. This makes it easy to update, fix or expand features. We also used a clean, layered setup, where everything is held neatly at one place, from storing known faces to logging new people.

The system gives real-time results like what it sees, and the time logs with details to every appearance. All this is useful for practical functions such as video analysis, attendance tracking, or even safety. Overall, the project proves that you do not need expensive hardware to run an effective face recognition system. In the future, we can make it smarter by adding alerts or allowing the model to switch to the model based on available resources. This setup is a great starting point for things such as school's attendance system, small monitoring systems.

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